

Assessment of Practice of Water Purification and Socio Economic Variabilities of Households in Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper assessed the practice of water purification and socio economic variabilities of households in Zamfara State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey research design was used. Population for this study was 592,106 households in Zamfara state. Sample size of 384 was selected using multistage sampling procedures which include cluster, proportionate and systematic sampling. Instrument for data collection was questionnaire developed by the researcher and validated by five (5) experts. The instrument was pilot-tested using Cronbach Alpha and a reliability co-efficient of 0.892 was obtained. SPSS version 25 was used for data analysis, descriptive statistics of frequency and percentages was used to analyze the demographic characteristics of the respondents, mean and standard deviation was used to answer research question 1 and 2. Inferential statistics of one-sampled t-test was used to answer hypotheses 1 on the practice of water purification, multiple regression analysis was use to answer research question 2 on socio economic determinants of households water purification. All hypotheses was tested at 0.05 level of significance, the result revealed that practice of water purification among households in Zamfara State is significant ($p = 0.000$); socio economic determinants (income, education and occupation) on practice of water purification among households in Zamfara State is significant ($p = 0.000$) Based on the results, the study concluded that households in Zamfara State demonstrate significant positive practices of water purification which are influenced by socioeconomic factors such as income, education, and occupation. Based on the conclusion, the study recommended that Zamfara State government should provide subsidies or incentives for water purification tools and products to encourage wider adoption of purification practices. NGOs and international development agencies should tailor their water purification interventions to address socio economic disparities, focusing on low-income and less-educated households.

Keywords: Practice, Water purification, socioeconomic, Household

Introduction

Water contamination is primarily caused by the discharge of untreated wastewater from enterprises. The effluent or sewage discharge from various enterprises which contains varying levels of contaminants is dumped into rivers or other water sources. Treatment for drinking water production involves the removal of contaminants and/or inactivation of any potentially harmful microbes from raw water to produce water that is pure enough for human consumption without any short term or long term risk of any adverse health effect. In general terms, the greatest microbial risks are associated with ingestion of water that is contaminated with human or animal (including bird) faeces. Faeces can be a source of pathogenic bacteria, viruses, protozoa and helminths (WHO, 2020). The size and capacity of water treatment systems vary widely ranging from simple households units to small facilities that serve manufacturing industries to large scale centralized water treatment plants dedicated to cities and towns. Selection of specific treatment processes depends upon factors such as intake water quality, degree of purification required, intended water use, flow capacity requirements, government regulations, available capital and the operations as well as maintenance costs involved (Centre for Disease Control, 2022). The wastewater may have a high proportion of organic and inorganic contaminants at the initial discharge. Industries generate wastewater as a result of fabrication processes, processes dealing with paper and pulp, textiles, chemicals from various streams such as cooling towers, boilers and production lines (Singh, *et al*, 2018).

Objective of the study

The main purpose of this study is to assess the practice of water purification and socio economic variabilities of households in Zamfara State. Therefore, the study was guided by the following specific objectives, to:

1. Assess practice of households on water purification in Zamfara State;
2. Assess socio economic determinants of practice of water purification among households in Zamfara state.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. What are practices of water purification among households in Zamfara State?

2. What are the socio economic determinants of practices of households on water purification in Zamfara state?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. **H₀₁**: Practice of water purification among households in Zamfara State is not significant;
2. **H₀₂**: There is no significant difference in socio economic determinants (income, education and occupation) of practices of water purification among households in Zamfara state;

Methodology

This paper assesses practice of water purification and socio economic variabilities among households in Zamfara State. In order to achieve this purpose, research design, population of the study, sample and sampling technique, data collection instrument, validation of the instrument, data collection procedure and procedure for data analysis were discussed.

Descriptive research design was used for this study. According to Shields and Rangarajan, (2013), descriptive research is used to describe characteristics of a population or phenomenon being studied. It does not answer questions about how/when/why the characteristics occurred. Rather it addresses "what" question (what are the characteristics of the population or situation be studied). Descriptive research design focuses on the people and their beliefs, opinions, perception and behaviours (Nwana, 2015).

The population of this study comprise of five hundred and ninety two thousands, one hundred and six (592,106) households from all fourteen (14) Local Government Areas (LGAs) in Zamfara State. This is based on the data obtained on Distribution of Households by Type of Housing Unit from the National Population Commission (NPC, 2020), Zamfara State office, Gusau.

A sample size of three hundred and eighty four (384) Households participated in the study. This is based on the sample size selection table by Research Advisors (2006), which suggests that for a population of 592,106a sample size of 384 is sufficient for generalization at a 95 % confidence level and at 5.0 % margin of error. Multistage sampling technique was used by the researcher that comprises of cluster, proportionate and systematic sampling which Alvi (2016), explained that, this type of sampling technique are being used when the elements of the population are more than one and spread. Cluster sampling technique was used by the researcher to group or to divide the state based on three

(3) senatorial zones (i.e Zamfara central, north and west). A proportionate sampling technique was used to select one (1) Local Government (Gusau) from Zamfara central, One (1) Local Government (Kaura Namoda) from Zamfara north and 2 Local Government (Talata Mafara & Gummi) from Zamfara west senatorial zone. Thus, Zamfara central has only four (4) Local Governments, Zamfara north also has four (4) local governments while Zamfara west has (6) Local Governments respectively. In order to be fair to the population distribution, the research chooses two (2) Local Government from Zamfara west and one (1) each from Zamfara north and Zamfara central zones.

A proportionate sampling procedure was adopted to compose the sample size of 384 among the four (4) selected Local Government Areas where Gusau has 130 numbers of respondents, Kaura Namoda 100, Talata Mafara 78, and Gummi 76, Which Sulaiman (2015), explained that proportionate sampling is used when the elements of the populations vary considerably in size because, it assures that those in larger size will have the same probability of getting the larger sample size as those in the smaller size will also have the same probability of getting small sample and systematic sampling was used for selection of households on the basis of numerical sequence.

Table 1: Sample Size Distribution

S/N	Senatorial Districts	Sampled Local Gov't Areas	Sampled Households
1.	Zamfara Central	Gusau	130
2.	ZamfaraNorth	Kaura-Namoda	100
3.	ZamfaraWest	Talata-Mafara	78
		Gummi	76
Total	03	04	384

A questionnaire titled “Assessment of Practice of Water purification among Households” (APWPH) was developed by the researcher. The questionnaire consists of two parts- A and B. Part A obtained the information of households socio demographic characteristics, parts B obtained households information on practice of water purification using Likert scale level of agreement of Most Often (MO), Often (O), Not Always (NA) and Not At All (NAA) with the value of 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

The instrument was subjected and validated by 5 experts who scrutinized the instrument gave suggestions and corrections where incorporated in the final draft. The validated instrument was subjected to reliability test using Cronbach Alpha to test the internal consistency via statistical package for social science (SPSS) and reliability level of 0.892 was obtained. An introductory letter from the Head of Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria was obtain by the researcher to enable him collect data from the sampled households, where 384 questionnaires were duly distributed to 384 households through their consent by the researcher with the help of three (3) research assistants and 384 questionnaires was retrieved.

For the analysis of the data that was collected from the households, the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) Version 25 was used to analyze the data obtained from the respondents. The demographic characteristics of respondents were computed using frequency and percentage. Research question 1 and 2 was answered using mean and standard deviation, One sample-t-test was used to test hypotheses 1 on practice of water purification, while multiple regression analysis was used to test hypothesis 2 on socio economic determinants of water purification among households in Zamfara state. All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

All data collected on demographic characteristics of the respondents were tabulated using frequencies and percentages as indicated in Table 2

Table 2: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age Range in Years		
18 – 40	240	62.5
40 and above	144	37.5
Total	384	100.0
Gender		
Male	297	77.3
Female	87	22.7
Total	384	100.0
Income		
Less than 30,000	89	23.2

30,000 to 50,000	167	43.5
50,000 to 100,000	80	20.8
More than 100,000	48	12.5
Total	384	100.0
Educational Qualification		
Primary	14	3.6
Secondary	64	16.7
Tertiary	288	75.0
Non Formal	18	4.7
Total	384	100.0
Occupation		
Civil Servant	237	61.7
Business Man	81	21.1
Farmers	36	9.4
Others	30	7.8
Total	384	100.0

Table 2 provides the demographic characteristics of the respondents in the study. The data was presented across three variables: age range in years, gender, income, educational qualification and occupation, with corresponding frequencies and percentages. In terms of age distribution, the majority of respondents 62.5 %, (240 respondents) were between 18 and 40 years old, while 37.5 % (144 respondents) were 40 years and above. The gender composition of the sample was predominantly male, with 77.3 % (297 respondents) being men and 22.7 % (87 respondents) being women.

Regarding income levels, the largest group of respondents 43.5 %, (167 respondents) reported earning between 30,000 to 50,000 Nigerian Naira. The second largest income group was those earning less than 30,000 Naira, accounting for 23.2 % (89 respondents). 20.8 % (80 respondents) reported earning between 50,000 to 100,000 Naira, while the smallest group (12.5 %, 48 respondents) earned more than 100,000 Naira.

Educational qualifications of the respondents showed that the vast majority 75 %, (288 respondents) had tertiary education. Secondary education was the next most common, with 16.7 % (64 respondents). Only 3.6 % (14 respondents) had primary education, while 4.7 % (18 respondents) had non-formal education.

In terms of occupation, civil servants constituted the largest group, representing 61.7 % (237 respondents) of the sample. Businessmen made up 21.1 % (81 respondents), while farmers accounted for 9.4 % (36 respondents). The remaining 7.8 % (30 respondents) were classified under "Others" for their occupation.

Research Question One: What are the practices of households on water purification in Zamfara State?

Table 3: Mean Scores of Responses on the practices of households on water purification in Zamfara State

S/N	Item	Mean	Std Dev
1.	I filter my water before drinking in order to prevent contaminants.	3.49	0.78
2.	I boil my drinking water for the purpose of disinfection.	3.13	0.98
3.	I do keep my water for the suspended particles to settle down before drinking.	3.13	0.95
4.	I use alum for my drinking water.	2.80	1.02
5.	I do keep my water in the sun in order to reduce the growth of some pathogenic organisms. Such as bacteria.	2.43	0.99
6.	I fetch my drinking water from borehole and well.	3.39	0.83
7.	I use water from open source like rivers and lakes for drinking.	2.98	1.11
8.	I use nets, clean rags and sievers as filters to purify my drinking water.	2.89	0.87
9.	I use chlorine for water disinfection.	2.72	1.07
10.	I use to store water in clean and safe container after purification	3.32	0.91
Aggregate		3.03	

(Decision Mean – 2.50)

Table 3 outlines the mean scores of responses regarding the practices of households on water purification in Zamfara State. The mean scores indicated that the most common practice among households was filtering water before consumption, with a mean score of 3.49, suggesting a strong

emphasis on preventing contaminants. Following closely, fetching drinking water from boreholes and wells, which scored 3.39, highlighted the reliance on these sources for perceived safety.

Boiling water for disinfection and allowing suspended particles to settle both received mean scores of 3.13, indicating that these practices were also relatively prevalent. However, the use of alum to purify drinking water was less common, with a mean score of 2.80. The practice of exposing water to sunlight to reduce pathogenic growth scored even lower at 2.43, reflecting limited engagement with this method among households.

The utilization of open sources like rivers and lakes for drinking water presented a score of 2.98, suggesting that some households depended on these sources, although it was not the predominant practice. Additionally, the use of nets, clean rags, and sievers as filters was noted with a mean score of 2.89, indicating a moderate level of reliance on these makeshift filtration methods. Chlorine usage for disinfection was the least favoured practice, scoring 2.72.

Finally, the practice of storing purified water in clean and safe containers received a mean score of 3.32, highlighting the importance placed on safe storage after purification. The overall aggregate mean score of 3.03 indicated that households in Zamfara State generally engaged in water purification practices.

Research Question Two: What are the socio economic determinants of practice of households on water purification in Zamfara State?

Table 4: Mean Score of responses on the socio-economic determinants of the practice of households on water purification in Zamfara State

	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean Difference
Practice (Constant)	3.03	0.57	
Income	2.23	0.94	0.80
Educational Qualification	2.81	0.57	0.22
Occupation	1.63	0.94	1.40

Table 4 shows the mean score on the socio economic determinants of the practice of households on water purification in Zamfara State with a mean of 3.03, 2.23, 2.81 and 1.63 and mean difference of

0.80, 0.22 and 1.40. Based on this outcome, socio-economic factors (income, educational qualification and occupation) determine the practice of water purification among households in Zamfara State.

Hypothesis One: Practice of water purification among households in Zamfara State is not significant

Table 5: One-Sample t-test Analysis of Practice of water purification among households in Zamfara State

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Df	t-value	p-value
Practice	384	3.03	0.57	383	103.430	0.000
Test Mean	384	2.50	0.00			

Calculated $p < 0.05$, calculated $t\text{-value} > 1.972$ at $df\ 383$

The result of the one-sample t-test statistics in Table 5 reveals that the practice of water purification among households in Zamfara State is significant because the calculated p-value of 0.000 is lower than the 0.05 level of significance and the calculated t-value of 103.430 is higher than the 1.972 critical t-value at 383 degrees of freedom (df). Therefore, the hypothesis which stated that the practice of water purification among households in Zamfara State is not significant was rejected. This means that households in Zamfara State are generally engaged in water purification practices.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in practice of water purification among households on socio-economic determinants (income, education and occupation) in Zamfara State.

Table 6: Multiple Regression Analysis on Practice of Water Purification and Socio-economic Determinants

Model Summary					
R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson	
.157	.025	0.017	.56895	1.658	
ANOVA					
Model	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	3.097	3	1.032	3.189	0.000
Residual	123.008	380	.324		
Total	126.105	383			
Coefficients					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	3.485	.205		17.001	.000
Income	.092	.033	.152	2.842	.000
Educational Qualification	.058	.056	.057	1.035	.000
Occupation	.054	.035	.089	1.544	.000

Table 6 shows the outcome of multiple regression analysis on the practice of water purification among households and socio economic variables (income, education and occupation) in Zamfara State. The overall model shows a statistically significant relationship ($F(3, 380) = 3.189, p < .005$), indicating that at least one of the predictors (income, educational qualification and occupation) has a significant influence on the practice of water purification. However, the amount of variance explained by the model is relatively low, with an R-squared of 0.025, suggesting that only about 2.5 % of the variability in the practice of water purification can be explained by these socio-economic variables.

Examining the individual predictors, income, educational qualification and occupation each have statistically significant relationships with knowledge of water purification. Specifically, income ($\beta = 0.152, p < .005$), educational qualification ($\beta = 0.057, p < .005$), and occupation ($\beta = 0.089, p < .005$) all positively influence practice, as indicated by their positive standardized coefficients. Based on this outcome, the hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in practice of water purification among households on socio economic variables (income, education and occupation) in Zamfara State was rejected.

Discussion of findings

The finding from the study revealed that the practice of water purification among households in Zamfara State is significant ($p = 0.000$). This means that households in Zamfara State engage in significant water purification practices. This finding agrees with the study by Miner et al. (2015) in Lamingo, Plateau State, Nigeria, which found that 54% of households practised at least one method of water purification. The common methods included the addition of alum (43.3 %), boiling (24.9 %), and filtration (21.4 %). The significant practice of water purification in both studies suggests a growing awareness of the importance of treating water at the household level in different parts of Nigeria.

Similarly, the result is consistent with Simon, *et al* (2020) on an assessment of Water Supply, Sanitation and Hygiene Practices among Households in Cross River State, Southern Nigeria, which reported that 43 % of households had access to improved drinking water sources and practiced some form of water treatment. This further supports the notion that households across various Nigerian states are increasingly adopting water purification practices.

The finding from the study revealed that socio economic determinants (income, education and occupation) on practice of water purification among households in Zamfara State is significant ($p = 0.000$). This means that socioeconomic factors such as income, education, and occupation significantly influence the practice of water purification among households in Zamfara State.

Abera *et al.* (2020) observed in their study in rural Ethiopia that poor practices related to water, sanitation and hygiene were more common among residents with lower socioeconomic status. They noted that education level in particular had a significant influence on WASH practices. The findings are also consistent with Rima et al. (2017), who reported a statistically significant difference in practices

regarding water sanitation and hygiene based on mothers' education levels in rural Nepal. Those with higher education demonstrated better positive practices.

Similarly, Katkuri (2021) conducted a study on practices on sanitation, water and hygiene among mothers of under-five children in villages around the Rural Health Training Center, Gummadidala, India and found that mothers' education levels were associated with their practices related to water hygiene in rural India. Mothers with higher education were more likely to take precautions like boiling water for infant formula. Bikes, *et al* (2017) assessed the practice of mothers/caregivers on household water treatment methods in Northwest Ethiopia and reported that being an urban resident, which is often linked to higher socioeconomic status, was significantly associated with better household water treatment practices in northwest Ethiopia.

Conclusion

The paper concluded that, households in Zamfara State engage in significant water purification practices, likewise socioeconomic factors such as income, education and occupation significantly influence the practice of water purification among households in Zamfara State.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion, the paper recommended the following:

1. The Zamfara State government should provide subsidies or incentives for water purification tools and products to encourage wider adoption of purification practices.
2. NGOs and international development agencies should tailor their water purification interventions to address socioeconomic disparities, focusing on low-income and less-educated households.

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